

ELEPHANT

IN THE LAB

SHORT ANALYSIS

Authorship in Business and Economy

Short title	Authorship in Business and Economy
Long title	Bibliometrics of the 20 highest performing authors in Business, Management, and Accounting as well as Economics, Econometrics, and Finance
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Description

The number of authors per article in the subject area *Business, Management, and Accounting* is 2.6 on average with a maximum of 8 authors. The mean number of coauthors is increasing by 0.1 per year in the respective time period (Figure 1). The articles in this analysis ($n = 999$) were cited 10.5 times on average with a maximum of 138 citations.

The number of authors per article in the subject area *Economics, Econometrics, and Finance* is 2.8 on average with a maximum of 9 authors (Figure 2). The mean number of coauthors is increasing by 0.1 per year in the respective time period. The articles in this analysis ($n = 1077$) were cited 8.4 times on average and 188 as maximum.

NUMBER OF AUTHORS PER ARTICLE IN THE SUBJECT AREA BUSINESS, MANAGEMENT, AND ACCOUNTING

Increase of co-authors per year = 0.1
Number of articles = 999

Figure 1: [Boxplot](#) of the number of authors per paper in the subject area *Business, Management, and Accounting*. The box denotes 25–75% of the values with the median (bold line) in it. The small circles are outliers. Due to a limitation of the y-axis, some outliers are not shown. The yellow line shows a linear model of the mean number of authors per article with a confidence interval of 0.95 shown in light grey. Data source: Scopus. CC BY 4.0 Schmidt, Fecher, Kobsda.

NUMBER OF AUTHORS PER ARTICLE IN THE SUBJECT AREA ECONOMICS, ECONOMETRICS, AND FINANCE

Increase of co-authors per year = 0.1
Number of articles = 1077

Figure 2: [Boxplot](#) of the number of authors per paper in the subject area *Economics, Econometrics, and Finance*. The box denotes 25–75% of the values with the median (bold line) in it. The small circles are outliers. Due to a limitation of the y-axis, some outliers are not shown. The yellow line shows a linear model of the mean number of authors per article with a confidence interval of 0.95 shown in light grey. Data source: Scopus. CC BY 4.0 Schmidt, Fecher, Kobsda.

Methodology

The results of the Advanced search in Scopus were restricted by an algorithm with

- a time period of publishing (2010 to 2016)
- the document types (articles or reviews),

- and a quantitative limitation regarding the publication output (articles by the 20 highest performing authors with the most Scopus listed articles in every subject area).

For details and code see Schmidt et al. [2017](#).

References

Schmidt, M., Fecher, B., Kobsda, C. (2017). Methodology for the analysis of authors using meta data from Scopus. [Elephant in the lab](#). [Link](#).